

JALOLIDDIN MANGUBERDI - A SYMBOL OF HEROISM

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Abstract

This article provides information about the struggle and heroism of Jaloliddin Manguberdi for the freedom and freedom of his homeland. The article describes Jaloliddin Manguberdi's fight against the Mongols. It is also explained that he was able to unite the neighbouring countries in the fight against the Mongols, as well as to establish his own state and rule large territories until his death.

Keywords: Khorezmshah Ghazna, Parvan, Genghis Khan, Khoru, India, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Khalsultan, Sind Mongol, Kandahar.

INTRODUCTION

As we look at the many years of priceless history of our country, our compatriots who showed bravery and selflessness in the great work of protecting our country from invaders and evil forces, and protecting the independence and freedom of our nation, are the heroes of our nation. We feel proud of their presence. One of them was Jaloliddin Manguberdi, a bright and last representative of the Anushtegin dynasty, a strong politician, a great diplomat. This person, who deserved the recognition of Genghis Khan and fought against the tyranny of the Mongols, occupied an important place in the history of not only Central Asia, but also the Middle East, South Asia, and the Caucasus. The exact date of birth of Jaloliddin, who lived only 32 years but left an indelible mark in world history, is not known, but his death is officially called 1198. He was the eldest son of Khorezmshah Alauddin Muhammad and Aychechak. At the initiative of his mother, Jaloliddin learned military art from Agha Kuzbor. Kuzbor Agha teaches him to ride a horse, play swordsmanship and shoot archery. He was brought up to be able to clearly prove his opinion on various issues from a young age. However, the inner leadership in the palace noticed all the movements, knew that it was a difficult task to prevent or stop these situations, but could not tell his father about them.

In the following article, we will touch on some aspects of Jaloliddin Khorazmshah's military life.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The level of studying the history of the Anushtegin-Khorazmshah state can be divided into 4 stages.

1st stage- coverage in Arabic sources: This includes sources created during the Khorezmshah period and sources created in later periods. In these sources, the economic, political structure, cultural development of the Khorezmshah state, the history of the rulers, especially the activities of Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi are widely covered.

2nd stage - study by foreign scientists. The history of the Khorezmshah state has been widely studied by foreign scholars. O. Masalieva conducted research on this issue. Aydin Tonari's work titled "Jalaluddin Khorezmshah and his era" describes the state of the Khorezmshahs and their relationship with the Mongols¹.

3rd stage - the history of the Khorezmshah state has been extensively studied by scholars even during the period of the former Soviets. Although the bravery of Jaloliddin Manguberdi was mentioned in the works created during this period, the politics of Muhammad Khorezmshah were analyzed².

4th stage - learning during the years of independence. The history of the Khorezmshahs began to be widely studied. Especially in 1999, the holding of an international conference in connection with the 800th anniversary of Jaloliddin Manguberdi made it possible to further expand the research on the Khorezmshah state. During this period, scientific literature was published by O. Masharipov, Sh. Saidov, I.M. Jabborov, S. Saburova, O. B. Boriev, N. T. Toshev³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Leaving the palace in the capital, which had become a hotbed of conspiracy, Jaloliddin defeated the 700-horse Mongol army blocking his way with 300 horsemen at the threshold of Nisa. Arriving in the city of Ghazna, he begins to gather new strength. He won over the Mongols several times. Jaloliddin defeats the Mongols besieging the city of Kandahar after fierce battles, military forces started to join Jaloliddin's army in Ghazna from all directions. The troops of Khalaj tribe commander Saifiddin Ig'raq, Balkh governor Azam Malik, Afghan army commander Muzaffar Malik and Qarluq leader Al-Hasan joined Jaloliddin⁴. Jaloliddin also destroyed the Mongol troops besieging Valiyan fortress. The news of this victory reached Genghis Khan, and Genghis Khan, greatly disturbed by this, sent his 45,000-strong army under the leadership of his most tried general, Shiki Khutuku Nuyon, against Jaloliddin. The two large armies meet on a low plain near Parwan, Afghanistan. In this battle, Sultan Jaloliddin once again showed his military genius. The battle was merciless and merciless. In battle, Jaloliddin used his own unique methods. In this battle, Jaloliddin's army defeats the powerful and cunning Mongol army. The defeat of the Mongols in the battle near Parvan was their first major defeat during their attacks on the Khorezmshah state. Thus, Genghis Khan's opponent feels that he is worthy of him, and he realizes that now is the time to prepare for a decisive battle, and begins to make great preparations for the battle. One of the most remarkable aspects of Jaloliddin's great victory near Parvan was that the inhabitants of several cities heard about this victory, were inspired by it, rebelled against the Mongols, and killed their viceroys. At the same time, he did not even imagine that as a result of Parvan's victory, he would cause great worries to Jaloliddin. During the division of the spoils captured in this battle, Jaloliddin broke out among the warlords by stealing a noble Arabian horse. Jaloliddin could not reconcile them. Due to the conflict, the commanders Sayfiddin Aghroq, Azam Malik and Muzaffar Malik lost their army with more than 25 thousand soldiers each (unfortunately, the Mongols later defeated and destroyed all of them separately). Due to this terrible situation, Jaloliddin's military power was greatly

weakened. Jaloliddin, helpless in front of a powerful enemy with a small army, began to prepare to cross over to India. However, while the ships were being prepared on the banks of the Sind (Indus) river, Genghis Khan, who personally marched against him, arrived with his troops. The balance of power was sharply in favor of Genghis Khan. Jaloliddin, thinking of defeat, orders his mother, wives and daughters to be drowned in the river by their own will so that they will not be captured and insulted by the enemy. But when the Mongols captured Jaloliddin's 8-9-year-old son and brought him to Genghis Khan, the king ordered to pull out his heart and throw it to a dog. The command is executed. The famous historian Shahabeddin al-Nasawi, who was the owner of one of the castles in Nisa province, served as one of Jaloliddin's most trusted officials from 1224 to 1231, that is, until his death⁵. He was always with Jaloliddin and wrote down what he saw and knew. According to him, the historic battle for life and death between the armies of these two great generals will take place on November 24, 1221. Historian Juvaini describes this event as follows⁶: "Sultan Jaloliddin was left between water and fire in the morning of that day. On one side is the sizzling river Sindh, and behind it is the burning Mongol army. In such a difficult situation, the Sultan did not lose himself and chose the path of confrontation with the enemy". In this matchless battle, Jaloliddin fought with all his courage, skill and strength, surprising even the Mongol armies. But Genghis Khan's army was increasing every hour. With a last great effort, forcing the troop to retreat a little, he turned back the reins, and, removing his bridle, whipped the horse. Jumps from the bank into the river from a distance of 10 gas or more. Like a ferocious lion, he crossed the river and reached the other shore. Genghis Khan saw this situation and brought his horse to the river bank. The Sultan crossed the river with a sword, a spear and a shield. Seeing this situation, Genghis Khan turned to his sons and said⁷: "The son of a brave father should be like this! If he escapes from the two whirlpools of water and fire and reaches the coast of salvation, he will be born with countless deeds and countless dangers".

The echoes of the battle on the banks of the river Sindh have reached us from the depths of the past through various means. According to the writings of the English orientalist G. Raverty and the Russian scientist and traveler G. E. Grumm-Grjimaylo, the place where the Sindh River crossed Jaloliddin and the nearby desert was called "Choli (Joli) Jaloliddin" after him, and this name has been preserved until now.

According to some scholars who traveled to Mongolia at the beginning of the 20th century, there is a mausoleum of Genghis Khan in a place called Ejen Khoru in Inner Mongolia (on the territory of China). Ceremonies and actions are sometimes held here for the spirit of Genghis Khan. For example, every morning, the priests count 150 big and small victories of Genghis Khan during his military campaigns, and first of all, they mention Genghis Khan's victory over Jaloliddin (Nuryogdi Toshev, a treatise entitled "Jaloliddin Manguberdi". T. Komolot. 1999.20-21 pages). This information definitely indicates that during the military campaigns of Genghis Khan, he did not meet another opponent who could stand up to him like Jaloliddin.

After crossing the river Sind, Jaloliddin decided to collect the remaining warriors and try to establish relations with the rulers of several states in the territory of Northern India. But before the exhausted and small army under the leadership of Jaloliddin had time to recover, the king of

the Shatra region attacked them with 1,000 cavalry and 5,000 foot soldiers, taking advantage of the army's plight. Trusting in God, Jaloliddin led his army to war with all his might, and only because of his bravery did the warriors of Khorezm defeat the Indian army. As a result, the warriors of the Shatra king surrendered and went to the side of Jaloliddin. Jaloliddin improves the situation of his army, gradually the number and power of his army increases. He even mints coins in his name, and his name is added to the sermon in prayers in all regions⁸.

Jaloliddin ruled India for three years and seven months, experiencing various battles and conspiracies. Here he built a great state. New forces will join him from all around. Jaloliddin expanded the borders of his state, gathered a lot of power, and then made it his heart to settle accounts with the Mongols. For this purpose, he started the first of his military campaigns by invading Iraq. Respectable officials of Iraq and Iran went to Jaloliddin's side. The rulers of Egypt and Syria also sent ambassadors to Jaloliddin. Until 1226, Jaloliddin conquered Azerbaijan and Georgia in battle. On September 5, 1227, Jaloliddin defended Iran from the Mongols near Isfahan and won a great victory over them.

Due to the death of Genghis Khan this year, the Genghisians were busy with their internal affairs for a while. Some of their leaders will even try to be on good terms with Jaloliddin from now on.

In 1230, when Jaloliddin was besieging the city of Hilot, he received a name from his sister Kholsultan (who was captured by the Mongols and married to Genghis Khan's eldest son Joji and had a child with her). In a letter, his sister informs Jaloliddin that the Khagan knows about his power, property, and capabilities, and that the Khagan agreed with Jaloliddin on border issues and decided to live in peace. He also advises him to fight and take revenge against the Mongols if he has the strength to resist them, or to make peace with them when they want peace. But Jaloliddin leaves this letter of his sister unanswered and ignores this opportunity to restore the state of Khorezmshahs. At the same time, Konya sultan of Ani province in Asia Minor, Olaviddin Qayqubad joined Jaloliddin of his own free will, but due to some of Jaloliddin's mistakes, there was a coldness between them and he prepared a conspiracy against Jaloliddin. Qayqubad also managed to involve the rulers of countries such as Sham, Northern Mesopotamia and a number of other cities in the plot. But Jaloliddin does not pay much attention to this movement. It was during these times that Jaloliddin's character showed some inexplicable indifference and laziness in the action against the Mongol troops. In August 1230, a historic battle took place between the large combined forces of the conspirators and the forces of Jaloliddin. Jaloliddin's troops retreated to the territories of Azerbaijan after seeing great losses⁹. Olavuddin Muhammad III, the ruler of the Ismailis in Azerbaijan, sends a secret letter to the Mongols about his weakening. The goal was to destroy Jaloliddin at the hands of the Mongols. Mongols use this opportunity to send a special large army against Jaloliddin. Since then, Jaloliddin's luck has turned away, and the attention of his friends and relatives begins to decrease.

Even his most trusted prime minister, Sharaf al-Mulk, changed his attitude towards him and dared to organize a conspiracy against Jaloliddin. Jaloliddin finds out about this and executes

his minister. Luck turned away from him. Jaloliddin, who has fallen into depression, has had many cases of drinking and drinking recently.

Unfortunately, Jaloliddin no longer had an army that could rely on them to oppose the Mongols. That is why he turns to all neighboring Muslim rulers for help. Unfortunately, in such difficult times, the rulers of the neighboring countries did not extend a helping hand and they left Jaloliddin alone. After that, Jaloliddin came to Isfahan with all his people through Asia Minor. Pursuing him, the Mongols attack his residence while he is fast asleep after another feast. With the help of Urkhan, Jaloliddin's closest emir, he escaped and survived only thanks to a miracle. Later, Jaloliddin escaped from the pursuit of the Mongols, and when he reached a village called Ayndar near Mayofarikin, he fell into the hands of Kurdish robbers. The Kurds will take everything he has. Their leader locks Jaloliddin in a house and appoints a guard. At that moment, a Kurd found out about this incident and came to the house where Jaloliddin was staying. This man's brother was killed by the Khorezmites during the siege of Hilot, and he was seeking revenge. Despite the guard's resistance, the unarmed Kurd stabs Jaloliddin to death. Jaloliddin is an incomparable boho who has survived so many years of intense and unparalleled battles, showing incomparable bravery, and this is how Jaloliddin's life path ends without fame. This event happened between August 17-20, 1231¹⁰. Then Khorezmshah Jaloliddin Manguberdi made an active effort to restore this kingdom and fight against the Mongol invaders, who were his successors, but unfortunately, he could not succeed. The internal conflicts, the infamous errors in domestic and foreign policy, characteristic of the feudal society of that time, did not allow him to do this.

CONCLUSION

Thus, Jaloliddin sacrificed his life for such a noble goal. The reasons mentioned above led to his tragic death. The expeditions of Genghis Khan's chief Mongol invaders to occupy the territories of Olavuddin Muhammad Khorezmshah's extremely large and powerful empire at the end of 1219 brought tragic black days to the people of the region due to the irreparable mistakes made by the king himself. Hundreds of towns and villages, various structures were destroyed and razed to the ground. The Khorezmshahs' failure to take into account the enemy's power, and the fact that they did not organize the defense of the peoples of the territories under their control caused the death of hundreds of thousands of people, the complete collapse of their kingdom, and their death ingloriously on a deserted island. It is extremely difficult to describe the state of the territories of our country after the Mongol invasion. Cities and villages that were developing in these areas turned into kultepa, life was completely destroyed, the streets, bazaars, oases, trade routes, which were crowded with residents, became empty. In particular, he gave the second son Chigatay the lands of our regions, Movaraunnahr, Eastern regions of Khorezm, Eastern Turkestan, Ettisuv, as well as Balkh, Badakhshan, Kabul, Ghazna, and the Sind River. These lands were called Chigatai ulus, and their rule began. The invasion of the Mongols pushed back the material and spiritual development of the people of our country by several hundred years. Written sources, rare, priceless books were burned and trampled. They killed most of our people's figures in various fields, scholars, great people. In general, development was dealt such a big blow that it was very difficult to restore it until the middle of the XIV century¹¹. Even in

such difficult times, our people sought and fought for freedom. Leading this struggle fell to Jaloliddin Manguberdi, a brave son of Turonzamin, especially the people of Khorezm. In fact, Jaloliddin, who had not opened one flower out of ten, and now it was time to play and laugh, faced very complicated and difficult life tests. He was able to withstand these tests. It is true that, as they say, an innocent god, he unknowingly made some serious mistakes and shortcomings during the struggle. But he fought hard all his life for his people, his country, his kingdom, his idea. He was able to fully demonstrate his leadership skills, bravery and other positive qualities. Showing a great example of heroism in this struggle, his young life was sacrificed, and the future generations were left with a bright memory. With the honor of independence, a special decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was announced to celebrate the birth of the national hero of our nation Jaloliddin Manguberdi and to perpetuate his honorable name.

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